

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

КРЕДИТОРСКАЯ ЗАДОЛЖЕННОСТЬ И ЕЕ РОЛЬ В ФИНАНСИРОВАНИИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ

Тажимаева К.А.

*PhD по экономическим наукам, доцент кафедры «Финансы и бизнес-аналитика»
Ташкентского государственного экономического университета*

ACCOUNTABLES AND ITS ROLE IN FINANCING THE ACTIVITIES OF THE ENTERPRISE

Tajibaeva K.

*PhD in Economics, Associate Professor of the Department of Finance and Business Analytics,
Tashkent State University of Economics*

Аннотация

В статье даны определения кредиторской задолженности, раскрыта их классификация. Достигнута главная цель, анализированы материалы на основе данных кредиторской задолженности акционерного общества «Ўзбекистон темир йўллари». Кроме того, рассмотрено влияние задолженностей на финансовое состояние предприятия и рекомендуются предложения которые позволят увеличить эффективность управления кредиторской задолженностью предприятия.

Abstract

The article gives definitions of accounts payable, discloses their classification. The main goal was achieved, materials were analyzed on the basis of data on accounts payable of the joint-stock company “Uzbekistan Railways”. In addition, the impact of debts on the financial condition of the enterprise is considered and proposals are recommended that will increase the efficiency of managing the accounts payable of the enterprise.

Ключевые слова: кредиторская задолженность, финансовое состояние, предприятия, эффективность, управление.

Keywords: accounts payable, financial condition, enterprises, efficiency, management.

A stable source of financial resources for any business entity is accounts payable, which is constantly at its disposal. These are, first of all, wage arrears, deductions to off-budget funds, reserves (for holidays), in accordance with the accounting policy, as well as advances from buyers, debts to suppliers and debts on taxes and fees. The formation of accounts payable to the employees of the enterprise for the payment of wages is due to the fact that in the composition of the proceeds from the sale there is necessarily a part of the funds for the reimbursement of labor costs.

The urgency of the problem is manifested in the fact that arising from the conduct of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise, forms a current and long-term diversion or attraction of funds, familiar to us as receivables and payables, they primarily affect solvency.

Unlike accounts receivable, accounts payable is perceived as a liability that adversely affects the activities of the enterprise.

Accounts payable is understood as a part of the property of the enterprise, which is the subject of legal obligations between the organization and its creditors. The economic component includes a part of the property of the enterprise (usually cash) and inventory items.

Types of accounts payable are shown in Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, according to the content of obligations, accounts payable can be associated with the acquisition of inventories (inventory), works and services (for purchased products, services and goods, as well as for bills presented for payment) and is not related with it (debts on settlements with the budget, debts to subsidiaries and affiliates, to the organization's personnel, to participants (founders) for the payment of income, other debts).

Figure 1. Classification of accounts payable¹

The organization owns and uses accounts payable, but it is obliged to return or pay this part of the property to creditors who have the right to claim it.

Thus, accounts payable have a dual legal nature: as part of the property, it belongs to the enterprise on the right of ownership or even on the right of ownership in relation to the money or things received on loan; as an object of legal obligations, it represents the debts of the enterprise to creditors, that is, persons authorized to claim or recover from the organization the specified part of the property.

In a simplified version, accounts payable is what this company owes to other persons. Taking into account the indicated signs, accounts payable can be defined as a part of the property of an enterprise that is the subject of debt obligations of the debtor organization to eligible persons - creditors arising from various legal grounds, subject to accounting and reflection in the balance sheet as debts of the organization - balance holder.

In cases where the debtor organization does not take any measures to voluntarily repay debts, creditors

still have the possibility of enforcement, which, depending on the nature of the accounts payable, is carried out in court or out of court.

The concept of accounts payable covers the debt obligations of the organization - the debtor, having a different origin.

Since accounts payable is one of the sources of funds at the disposal of the enterprise, it is shown in the liabilities side of the balance sheet. Accounts payable is kept separately for each creditor, and in generalizing indicators they reflect the total amount of accounts payable and give it, breaking it into groups.

The presence of accounts payable is an unfavorable factor for the enterprise, which significantly reduces the performance in assessing the financial condition of the enterprise, solvency and liquidity. Accounts payable arises if the date of receipt of services (goods, works, materials, etc.) does not coincide with the actual date of their payment.

Now we will analyze the assessment of the composition and structure of accounts payable based on the data of JSC JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" for 2019/2021.

Table 1

**Assessment of the composition and structure of accounts payable
JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" for 2019/2021²**

Composition of accounts payable	2019 г.		2020 г.		2021 г.		Change			
	Amount, billion sum	Share, %	Amount, billion sum	Share, %	Amount, billion sum	Share, %	Amount, billion sum		Growth rate, %	
							2019-2020	2020-2021	2019-2020	2020-2021
Short term - total	278,1	36,0	297,0	37,0	286,7	35,0	19,0	-10,3	106,8	96,5
Including: suppliers and contractors	49,6	6,4	52,1	6,5	53,3	6,5	2,5	1,2	105,1	102,3

¹ Арутюнов Ю. А. Финансовый менеджмент: учеб. пособие: рек. УМО Минобразования РФ; изд. 2-е, стер. М.: КНОРУС, 2007–94 с.

² Compiled by the author based on the materials of JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" for 2019/2021.

Indebtedness to the staff of the organization	51,3	6,7	49,4	6,2	41,9	5,1	-2,0	-7,4	96,2	85,0
Debt to state off-budget funds	32,7	4,2	31,9	4,0	33,9	4,2	-0,8	2,1	97,6	106,5
Debt on taxes and fees	55,6	7,2	49,3	6,1	42,3	5,2	-6,3	-7,0	88,7	85,8
Other creditors	88,8	11,5	114,3	14,2	115,1	14,1	25,5	0,8	128,7	100,7
Long-term - total	498,6	64	501,6	63	521,6	65	3,0	20,0	100,6	104,0
Total	776,7	100,0	798,7	100,0	808,4	100,0	22,0	9,7	102,8	101,2

Based on this table, it can be concluded that the amount of short-term accounts payable for 2020 compared to 2019 increased by 18,984,504 thousand soums (or by 106.83%) due to an increase of 2,527,630 thousand soums of debt to suppliers and contractors (or by 105.09%) and to other creditors by 25,504,238 thousand soums (or by 128.72%). An increase in settlements with suppliers and contractors could occur as a result of changes in the conditions for the purchase of goods or as a result of an increase in prices for them. According to the analysis, we see a decrease in debt on taxes and fees: in 2020 compared to 2019 by 6,285,281 thousand soums (or 88.70%) and in 2021 compared to

2020 by 6,996 817 thousand soums (or by 85.81%). This indicates a constant change in tax rates. In 2021, accounts payable increased by 9,682,910 thousand soums (or 101.21%) compared to 2020, to a greater extent due to an increase in debt to suppliers and contractors by 1,189,200 thousand soums (or 102.28%).

Thus, the increase in accounts payable in 2019-2021. is normal, but over the period under review, long-term accounts payable increases, which adversely affects the financial condition of the enterprise.

For a more detailed presentation of the calculated data, consider Figures 2.

Figure 2. Dynamics of short-term accounts payable of JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" for 2019/2021³

In order to reduce this debt to suppliers and contractors, it is possible to propose such measures as structuring accounts payable, in particular for suppliers and contractors, since they occupy a large share in the total debt, as well as offsetting.

Successful work to prevent overdue debts depends on the knowledge of not only each of the methods for solving this problem, but also the order of their application, depending on specific business situations.

For businesses, we can recommend the following proposals for managing accounts payable:

1. It is necessary to solve the problem of not only reducing accounts receivable, but also balancing it with accounts payable. When analyzing the relationship between receivables and payables, it is necessary to analyze the terms of a commercial loan provided to the company by suppliers of raw materials and materials.

2. To ensure the maximization of cash flow, the enterprise should use a wide variety of contract models

³ Compiled by the author based on the data in Table #3.

with flexible terms of the form of payment. In this case, various options are possible: from prepayment or partial prepayment to transfer for sale and a bank guarantee.

3. It is advisable to conduct a preliminary study of the solvency and reliability of the partner, his credit history, especially when concluding large contracts. However, for this it is necessary to have data banks, knowledge of the methodology and possible methods for assessing the obligation of counterparties. Such work can be performed by special agencies, credit bureaus, banks or analytical services of the enterprises themselves.

4. The search for joint solutions to prevent violations of the terms of contracts in terms of payments is the most rational and civilized way to forestall overdue debts. Thus, business partnerships and cooperation between the seller and the buyer can provide the fastest and most effective solution to problems and reduce overdue debts.

Summing up, it can be noted that the issue of accounts payable management is relevant for any enterprise. With proper debt management and using the above recommendations, the company can significantly improve its financial condition. The main thing is to correctly assess and analyze the state of the enterprise and choose the most suitable methods for yourself.

References

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 7 ноября 1994 года № УП-982 «Об образовании Государственно-акционерной железнодорожной компании «Узбекистон темир йуллари».
2. Аникина Е.С. Теоретические аспекты дебиторской задолженности, её сущность и классификация. Молодой ученый. -2019. С. 193-196.
3. Арутюнов Ю. А. Финансовый менеджмент: учеб. пособие: рек. УМО Минобразования РФ; изд. 2-е, стер. М.: КНОРУС, 2007–311 с.
4. Белкин В. Н. Организационный капитал предприятия / В. Н. Белкин, Н. А. Белкина // Экономика региона. – 2019. – Т. 12. – № 3. – С. 827.
5. Бочаров В.В. Управление денежным оборотом предприятий и корпораций. // Финансы и статистика.2018. -№17. –С. 141-159.
6. Желтухина М.А. Нормативное регулирование учета расчетов с поставщиками и подрядчиками // Молодой ученый. -2015. -№11. –С.837-843.
7. Кожина Е.А. Факторы, влияющие на оборачиваемость дебиторской задолженности // Финансы и кредит. -2017. -№21 (741).
8. Пятов М.Л. Управление обязательствами организации. Финансы и статистика. -2014. -250 с.
9. Данные Акционерного Общества «Ўзбекистон темир йўллари» за 2019/2021 гг.
10. Материалы государственной статистики за 2019/2021 гг.